

Stephen 20-18 TDP (Team description paper) soccer2D Simulation Iran Open RoboCup 2024

Taranom Zare¹, Mahya Khanmohammdi², Zahra Soleimani monem³, Ayda Shahabi⁴

¹ Shahed Hajar High school, Tehran

² Shahed Rah-e-Zeynab High school

³ Shahed Hajar High school, Tehran

⁴ Sarafraz High school, Tehran

Abstract. This report is written by the members of the Stephen 20-18 team consisting of 9th and 10th grade students in order to receive a license to participate in the Open RoboCup of Iran.

To write this article, reliable sources and football events have been used and a lot of effort has been spent on it. This team have changed things such as Pass, Shoot, Offside, Formation, Sample player and Press. It is hoped that Stephen's 20-18 team will be one of the 24 teams in the tournament

Keywords: Pass, Shoot, Offside, Formation, Sample player, Press, RoboCup

1 Introduction

RoboCup is an international joint project to promote AI, robotics, and related field. It is an attempt to foster AI and intelligent robotics research by providing a standard problem where a wide range of technologies can be integrated and examined. RoboCup chose to use soccer games as a central topic of research, aiming at innovations to be applied for socially significant problems and industries. The ultimate goal of the RoboCup project is by 2050, develop a team of fully autonomous humanoid robots that can win against the human world champion team in soccer. In order for a robot team to actually perform a soccer game, various technologies must be incorporated including: design principles of autonomous agents, multi-agent collaboration, strategy acquisition, real-time reasoning, robotics, and sensor-fusion. RoboCup is a task for a team of multiple fast-moving robots under a dynamic environment. RoboCup also offers a software platform for research on the software aspects of RoboCup. One of the major applications of RoboCup technologies is a search and rescue in large scale disaster. RoboCup initiated RoboCupRescue project to specifically promote research in socially significant issues.

Coding in football simulation is very complicated and needs to be simplified. One of the goals of programming is to use complex and incomprehensible functions to reach a simple and comprehensible output. Stephen 20-18's team is trying to Simulate a very simple and at the same time high-perception team and in this way have defined behaviors that are discussed below:

Table 1. The changes of the Stephen 20-18 Team

Behavior	class	Who has done
1 st -Sample_player	Strategic arrangement	<i>Mahya Khanmohammadi</i>
2 nd -Bhv_BasicMove	Chase_ball	<i>Taranom Zare</i>
3 rd -Bhv_BasicOffensiveKick	Shoot & New_shoot	<i>Mahya Khanmohammadi</i>
4 th -Bhv_BasicOffensiveKick	Pass	<i>Zahra Soleimani monem</i>
5 th -Bhv_BasicMove	Press	<i>Ayda Shahabi</i>

- 1- **Strategic arrangement.** The initial composition of the Stephen 20-18 team is based on the composition of 4-4-2(four-four-two). The reason for choosing this composition is based on recent research and conclusions of the composition of successful teams around the world, such as the composition of the Argentine national team in the 2022 World Cup game and also the composition of the Iranian national team in the game against Japan in the 2023 Asian Nations Cup.

Picture 1. Strategic arrangement

- 2- **Chase_ball.** This class, whose variable output is bool, is a behavior in which players are placed in specific positions according to the position of the ball and the corresponding post. It can be safely said that this behavior is one of the most important behaviors in the game. The order that is created in the game makes it possible to take control of the game. How this behavior works is given below:

The playing field is divided into 24 equal parts and is defined as an int output called `Number_and_region`. To get the region where the ball is located, we use the coordinates printed by the playing field and the `ballx` and `bally` variables. We did this with the int output that returns the length and width of the coordinates respectively.

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- 3- **Shoot.** The shoot class of the mentioned team has a behavior that is capable of checking the area around the player who is in a position to score a goal; in fact, it draws a triangle around the player that has the ability to check and estimate the correctness of his goal. This triangle has the initial coordinates one ahead of *ball_pos* and the distance between *ball_pos* and *left_goal* is 15 degrees. This behavior is to check this triangular area, it actually checks if there is a player from the opponent in this triangular area. And if there was, that player should not shoot. Also, in this class, a behavior is defined that gives the ability to check the offside error for the player who has the ball under his feet, which can prevent this important error
- 4- **New_shoot.** This function is defined in the *Bhv_Basicoffensivekick* section and has direct relationship with the shoot class in such a way that to make a shot from a strategic arrangement, it includes two strikers, two midfielders, two forwards and a normal player, which can be done by using back-to-back and confusing passes. He sent the ball to the door and scored.

Picture 2. Shoot and New_shoot

- 5- **Pass.** In the written code, the law is based on the fact that the players who were successful in passing to their teammates will receive positive points and if the players were not successful in passing, they will receive negative points and finally, to end the game, the players who are skilled in passing should be separated from the team and continue the game with skilled players who can pass better.
- 6- **Press.** The press code is written on the basis that the players of the team press the players of the opposing team at certain distances and prevent their movement and hard defense.

Picture 3. Press of opponent

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